

Electronic Theses and Dissertation (ETDs) by Indian Universities in Shodhganga Project: An Overview

Dr. Subhash Dhule

Librarian Government Law College, A road, Churchgate, Mumbai-400020 (India)

Corresponding author- **Dr. Subhash Dhule**

Email- glclibmum@gmail.com

Abstract: The present paper assesses the contribution of state Universities of Maharashtra in India's ETD Database Shodhganga. Electronic Theses and Dissertations (ETDs) are considered generally significant and broadly utilized assets by researchers in higher educational institutions. To share the research information among the Universities, the Shodhganga Project was initiated by INFLIBNET Centre, Ahmadabad, which provides free access to theses and dissertations through the archive. In this research paper researcher studies 13 state Universities of Maharashtra in which Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune has a maximum (12053) contribution and Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Aurangabad (5460) for uploading theses on Shodhganga.

Key Words: ETDs, SHODHGANGA, INFLIBNET, Theses and Dissertation, Repositories

Introduction: INFLIBNET Information and Library Network (INFLIBNET) Centre, Gandhinagar is an Autonomous Inter-University Centre (IUC) of the University Grants Commission, New Delhi (Ministry of Education, Govt. of India). It is a major National Programme initiated by the UGC in March 1991 as a project under the IUCAA, it became an independent Inter-University Centre in June 1996. INFLIBNET is involved in modernizing university libraries in India using state-of-art technologies for the optimum utilization of information. INFLIBNET is set out to be a major player in promoting scholarly communication among academicians and researchers in India.

Shodhganga : Shodhganga is the name coined to denote the digital repository of Indian Electronic Theses and Dissertations set up by the INFLIBNET center. The word "Shodh" originates from Sanskrit and stands for research and discovery. The "Ganga" is the holiest, largest, and longest of all rivers in the Indian Subcontinent. The Ganga is the symbol of India's age-ling culture and civilization, ever-changing, ever-flowing, ever-loved, and revered by its people, and has held India's heart captive and drawn uncounted million to her banks since the draw of history. Shodhganga stands for the reservoir of Indian Intellectual output stored in the repository hosted and maintained by the INFLIBNET Centre. Theses and dissertations are known to be a rich and unique source of information, often the only source

of research work that does not find its way into various publication channels. Theses and dissertations remain an untapped and under-utilized asset, leading to unnecessary duplication and repetition that, in effect, is the anti-theses of research and waste of huge resources, both human and financial. The UGC Notification (Minimum Standards & Procedure for Award of M.Phil. / Ph.D. Degree, Regulation, 2009 Amendment made in 2016) dated 5th May 2016 mandates submission of the electronic version of theses and dissertations by the researchers in universities with an aim to facilitate open access to Indian theses and dissertations to the academic community worldwide. Online availability of electronic theses through centrally-maintained digital repositories, not only ensures easy access and archiving of Indian doctoral theses but will also help in raising the standard and quality of research. This would overcome the serious problem of duplication of research and poor quality resulting from the "poor visibility" and the "unseen" factor in research output. As per the Regulation, the responsibility of hosting, maintaining, and making the digital repository of Indian Electronic Theses and Dissertations (called "Shodhganga"), accessible to all institutions and universities, is assigned to the INFLIBNET

Centre. (<https://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/>)(Source-<https://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/>)

Review of literature: Mapping the Contribution of Electronic Theses and Dissertations by the Universities of Assam to INFLIBNET Shodhganga Project: A Study, Parishmita Hazarika (2020) researcher study total of 12 Assam universities that have signed MoUs with Shodhganga, but only 10 universities contribute to Shodhganga. The two universities (Cotton University and the University of National Law and the Judicial Academy) have not yet proceeded to contribute their dissertations to the repository of shodhganga. b) It is found that Gauhati University (5551) has the highest total contributions, while Assam University (1436) has the second highest contributions, and Tezpur University (587) has the third highest contributions. c) Gauhati University's Department of Zoology has contributed top theses (370) in shodhganga, followed by Assam University of Ecology and Environmental Science (140) and Tezpur University's Department of Chemical Sciences (107). d) It is found that 6856 ETDs in English, 137 theses in the Assamese language, and 518 theses in other languages, including Bodo, Bengali, Manipuri, Hindi, INLIBNET Shodhganga Project: A Study, Parishmita Hazarika (2020) Availability of Electronic Theses and Dissertations (ETDs) of State Universities of Tamil Nadu in INFLIBNET Shodhganga Project: An Analysis, Sivakumaren K.S (2020) researcher study among 16 Universities, Anna University, Chennai has contributed the highest number of Theses (8905, 21.27%) in this project and placed in the 1st rank. The University of Madras has deposited 8617(20.59%) of Theses and is found in the 2nd place. Further, Bharathidasan University has deposited a good number (5707, 13.69%) of Theses and ranked in the 3rd place. Similarly, Manonmaniam Sundarnar University (5480, 13.09%), and Bharathiar University (4345, 10.38%) also contributed a considerable number of Theses and placed in 4th and 5th rank respectively. The contributions by Madurai Kamaraj (2214, 5.29%), Periyar University (1894, 4.52%), Alagappa

University (1880, 4.49%), and Annamalai University (1018, 2.43%) were found less among 16 Universities. The result shows that 2 top-ranked Universities contributed almost 41.85% of the Theses, whereas 3 Universities in the 3rd, 4th, and 5th ranks contributed 37.09% (15532) of the Theses. But, the remaining 11 Universities contributed only 21.06% (8816) of Theses. Hence, 31.25% of Universities are actively participating by means of contributing regularly and the remaining 68.75% of Universities are required to increase their contributions to this project.

The objective of the Study:

1. To study the top 10 Universities' Contributions to the Shodhganga project of India.
2. To study State Universities of Maharashtra signed MOU to the Shodhganga project.
3. To Analysis the contribution of ETDs by Maharashtra State Universities.

Scope and limitation of the Study:

1. The present study is limited to Maharashtra state University only.
2. The Present study is limited to data retrieved up to 20, February 2023.
3. The present study is limited to only Non-Agricultural Universities.

Research Methodology: The Present data were collected by visiting the Sodhgaganaga repository (<http://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/>) were data conducted from 1st February 2023 to 20th, February 2023. To trace the contribution of theses and dissertations to Shodhganga by the Maharashtra State Universities. After that retrieved data were tabulated and analyzed by using simple percentage, present in tabular and graphical form to represent the data.

Analysis and Interpretation of data:

Keeping in the view given in the above-mentioned objectives of the study the researcher studies the website of Shodhganga. The relevant data were extracted from the project website and analyzed by simple calculation method with Microsoft excel.

Table No.1. Sign MOU with INFLIBNETs Shodhganga.

SN	Year of MOU	Number of MOU	Percentage
1	2010	10	1.43%
2	2011	38	5.44%
3	2012	52	7.44%
4	2013	53	7.59%
5	2014	39	5.58%
6	2015	53	7.59%
7	2016	54	7.73%
8	2017	59	8.45%
9	2018	76	10.88%
10	2019	61	8.73%
11	2020	67	9.59%
12	2021	60	8.59%
13	2022	71	10.17%
14	2023	05 (Upto 01/02/2023)	0.71%
	Total MOU	698 (date- 01/02/2023)	

(Source:-

<https://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/newmoredetails/mou.html>) From the above table no.1 it is found that total 698 Universities MOU with INFLIBNETs

Shodhganga up to 01/02/2023. And Maximum Universities 76 MOU with Shodhganga in the year 2018.

Figure no.1

Table no. 2. Universities contribution in Shodhganga

Full Text These	Synopses/MRPs/FDF/ Fellowship	University Contributions	Universities+ CFTI/INIs Signed MOU
431060	9783	677	773

From the above table no.2 it is found that Full text These Uploaded up to date 01/02/2023 431060 and

synopses/MRPS/FDP/ Fellowship 9783, University Contribution 677 and Universities and CFTI/INIs Signed MOU 773 respectively.

Table no.3. Top Ten Universities Contribution in ETDs.

SN	Top Ten Universities	State	No of Theses	Rank
1	University of Madras	Tamil Nadu	13694	1
2	Anna University,	Tamil Nadu	13228	2
3	University of Calcutta	West Bengal	13028	3
4	Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune	Maharashtra	12052	4
5	Chhatrapati Sambhaji Maharaj University, Kanpur	Uttar Pradesh	10009	5
6	Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar Bihar University	Bihar	9675	6
7	Aligarh Muslim University	Uttar Pradesh	9348	7
8	V.B.S. Purvanchal University	Uttar Pradesh	8585	8
9	Punjab University	Punjab	8283	9
10	Andhra University	Andhra Pradesh	7779	10

(Source: - <https://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in/>)

From the above table no.3 it is found that top ten Universities of India uploaded theses and dissertation on Shodhganga in which University of Madras has rank one ((13694), Anna University,(13228), Savitirbai Phule University, Pune(12052), Chatrapati Sambhaji Maharaj University (10009), Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar Bihar University (9675), Aligarh Muslim university

(9348),V.B.S. Purvanchal University (8585), Punjab University (8283), Andhra University (7779). uploaded theses respectively.

Figure No.2. Top Ten Universities Contributed in ETDs

Table no. 4. Maharashtra State University wise contribution of theses in Shodhganga.

SN	Name of Maharashtra State University	No to These Uploaded	MOU date
1	Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune	12053	24/4/2011
2	Dr. Babsaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Aurangabad	5460	13/08/2013
3	Swami Ramanand Marathwada University, Nanded	5003	30/07/2013
4	Shivaji University, Kolhapur	4597	26/09/2011
5	Sant Gadge Baba Amravati University, Amravati	1277	26/09/2012
6	SNDT Women's University, Mumbai	1218	28/08/2012
7	University of Mumbai, Mumbai	1204	22/12/2014
8	Kavyitri Bahinabai Chaudhari North Maharashtra University, Jalgaon	1019	29/03/2014
9	Solapur University, Solapur	246	24/03/2015

	(Punyashlok Ahilyadevi Holkar Solapur University)		
10	Kavikulaguru kalidas Sanskrit University, Ramtek	155	10/11/2015
11	Gondwana university, Gadchiroli	150	06/12/2019
12	Rashtra Sant Tukdoji Maharaj Nagpur university, Nagpur	71	09/06/2016
13	Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Technical University, Lonar	39	26/09/2013
	TOTAL Theses Uploaded till 06/02/2023	32492	

From the above table no.4 it is found that Maharashtra state Universities (non Agricultural and non-technical) MOU with INFLIBNET Shodhganga. Two and three signed MOU with Shodhganga in the year 2011,2012,2014, and 2015 respectively. In the year 2016 and 2019 only one University signed. MOU with INFLIBNET respectively. In the Year 2013 three MOU signed by Shodhganga.

Findings and Conclusion:

Electronic Theses and Dissertation (ETDs) project of INFLIBNET by Shodhganga is great the greatest advantages of Electronic Theses and Dissertations are avoiding duplication in research work, ensuring quick retrieval of information, promoting resource sharing, and providing a permanent solution to the problem of the researcher. In India maximum, MOU with Shodhganga in 2018 (76) is 10.88%. and lowest MOU in the year 2010 (1.43%) The University of Madras has ranked first in India for the contribution of these uploaded on Shodhganga (13654) and Andhra University is tenth Rank Contribution of these uploaded (7779). In the Maharashtra Savitri Bai Phule Pune University, Pune has a major Contribution of Theses Uploaded in Shodhganga 12053, and Second one is Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Aurangabad contribution of 5460 these uploaded on Shodhganga as in third one is Swami Ramanand Teerth Marathwada University, Nanded has contributed 5003 theses uploaded on Shodhganga respectively.

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